

Earning Management in Islamic Ethical Perspective to Profit Quality Maslahah Improvement

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>The accounting scandal has proven that falsifying financial statements and managing income dishonestly has become rampant and has become part of the culture of many companies in the world. However, in meeting stakeholders' expectations, managers sometimes face a dilemma, displaying the financial statements as they are or taking actions in the financial statements to keep them fit and profitable. This dilemmatic position certainly has two contradictory sides that can lead managers who have fraud in accounting practices by holding FGDs with qualified informants at Kalla Group, Indonesia. This study aims to analyze the process and procedure of earning management carried out by the company. It also examines practice suitability, describes the application of efficient earnings, and formulates efficient EM forms with muamalah practices based on Islamic ethical values. The results of this study state that EM with Islamic ethical treatment is evidenced by several owners/principal statuses also acting as agents, meaning that it can minimize asymmetric information. Both parties between the agent and the principal, agree to run an efficient contract form to maximize utility and company goals. Efficient EM ensures that the financial reporting process maintains the applicable principles and rules. The practice of Efficient EM in the perspective of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group Company can be described by the strength of the Kalla Group's corporate values. Values such as work of worship, customer appreciation, faster the better, active together, align with Islamic values or ethics and professional ethics.</i></p>
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Introduction

The increasing number of recent accounting practice scandals has shown the spread of abusive and fraudulent practices among managers (Saona et al., 2020; Toumeh et al., 2020). Saona et al. (2020) found evidence that listed firms in Spain opportunistically manipulate their financial reports. Corporate governance systems determine this opportunistic managerial behavior materialized in the overstatement of financial statements. The discretionary capacity of executives to manage the earnings is reduced as the voting rights of the controlling shareholder increase. Wasan&Mulchandani (2020), in their study, revealed the occurrence of fraud and accounting scandals in India recorded since 2009 in terms of earnings management. Shoaib & Siddiqui (2020) also philosophically and empirically presents various facts and plots regarding scandals in earnings management. The accounting scandal has proven that falsifying financial statements and managing income dishonestly has become rampant and has become part of the culture of many companies in the world. It is well known that the general purpose of financial statements is to provide information about the financial position, performance, and cash flows of the company to users of financial statements to be used as a basis for decision making. Phenomena that often occur are related to earnings management (EM), which usually arises because of errors and omissions from the subject of financial management itself, directly or indirectly influenced by various internal and external factors. In general, EM is a choice by managers with accounting policies to achieve some specific goals (Gleason et al., 2000; Alvarado et al., 2020). Of course, financial statements are considered essential documents by most stakeholders. The income component in the financial statements is a component that has a significant influence on the decisions of various stakeholders. Income is seen as a component that can be changed to affect the investment decisions of shareholders and investors. Governments and other regulatory bodies may also be affected by the practice.

Agency theory highlights that these two parties, namely the agent and the principal, may have a conflict of interest. When this conflict of interest arises, managers responsible for using funds can become manipulative and opportunistic to accommodate specific interests (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Pelucio-Grecco et al., 2014; Gill et al., 2013). These actors concentrate only on their interests and not on the interests of shareholders. EM is an action that aims to maximize the utility of managers and goods to help them (managers) themselves by influencing the financial reporting process. Practices used to control income figures can be legal or illegal. EM

problems are not new in the preparation of financial reporting in business entities (See. Setiawati&Naim, 2001; Mardjono& Chen, 2020; El-Halaby et al., 2020). The pressure to generate profits is related to the income received by management, so EM is carried out to increase the profit figure, which causes an increase in the quality of the financial statements of companies in need.

The emergence of EM efficiency activities affects the market for companies to achieve profit targets following what is expected. This market pressure impacts revenue regulation, so managers try to increase company profits (Modigliani & Miller, 1963; Gaffar& Akal, 2021; Saif-Alyousfi et al., 2017). The decline in the quality of financial reports is the main impact resulting from EM. For this reason, EM can be detrimental to the company if it is implemented for an extended period. Particular objectives in EM are sometimes misinterpreted by interested parties in the company's financial statements. The purpose of presenting financial information is no longer closer to the essence of giving financial statements. Financial reports reflect the company's condition as a whole without causing a sense of doubt in it. Bias in the financial statements will cause errors in decision-making for the company. So that it can be detrimental to the company if this practice is carried out long enough. In Indonesia, many studies on EM have been carried out on various aspects of the company and relate it to corporate governance (e.g., Jaya &Narsa, 2020; Febrianti et al., 2020; Tandry et al., 2014). but the approach used is dominant with the conventional financial system approach, and it isn't effortless to find scientific studies on the concept of earning management with Islamic practice. In the Qur'an, many verses mention benefits either related to trade (business) or related to the procedures of human behavior in honest daily life. One of them is contained in Al-Quran Surah 41, namely Al-Fushshilat verse 35, which, if studied in-depth, reinforces that humans' benefits, if they can behave well and obey God's law, will benefit them. One of the economic aspects (muam'alah) in the Islamic legal system uses fiqhmuamalah. The principle of muamalahfiqh is "al ashlu fil mua'malati al ibahahhattayadulluaddhalilu 'ala tahrimiha" (original law in muamalah affairs is allowed, are there any arguments against it). One form of human muamalah development is accounting related to EM. Pava (1998) suggests that faith-based and/or spiritually driven ethics motivate individuals to incorporate the highest human and spiritual ideals into their business conduct. Plans can be manifested in the workplace environment, customer relations, pricing and profit margins, hiring and promotion, and competing in the marketplace. Applying the described Islamic ethical values is summarized in Islamic ethics; this concept will be a guideline in the practice of efficient EM in the company. Therefore, this study objectively analyzes the form of efficient EM treatment on the study subject. It also examines practice suitability, describes the application of efficient earnings, and formulates efficient EM forms with muamalah practices based on Islamic ethical values.

Agency theory states that the company can be viewed as a nexus of contract, i.e., the organization is broadly a set of agreements with many parties involved in the company (Gong & Tse, 2009). For example, contracts with employees (including managers), contracts with suppliers, contracts with providers of capital used by the company, and contracts with creditors. Regarding the existing agreements in the company, the company will try to minimize the contracting costs that arise in the contract relationship(Lambert, 2001), e.g., costs of negotiations, costs of monitoring and renegotiating contract performance and costs of possible bankruptcy. Earnings management can be explained from different perspectives and arguments. Some parties express different opinions.

On the other hand, earnings management is a form of earnings manipulation because earnings management is always based on the motivation to obtain personal gain by providing a picture of the company's performance that is not real. Even though the performance described is short-term performance. Suppose financial statement figures (especially profit figures) are engineered to meet the interests of managers, while the interests of other parties (such as investors and creditors) are ignored. In that case, earnings information is no longer neutral, contrary to the concept of neutrality formulated in the Basic Framework for Compiling and Presentation of Financial Statements(Mamo & Aliaj, 2014). Therefore, it takes Efficient EM to implement management activities, which sometimes arises paradox aspects regarding ethics for management because it influences managers and companies (Sayidah et al., 2020).

Earnings management benefits for managers are also carried out to reduce the possibility of being fired when managers have low performance. The good side of earnings management can be seen from the perspective of Efficient EM. From an efficient perspective, the level of earnings management can be considered good because it can increase contract efficiency. Efficient contracts allow managers to manage profits that can meet the two interests of the agent and the principal. Under these conditions, managers' interpretation of earnings management behavior in terms of bonus schemes, debt agreements, and political costs must be made carefully because these behaviors can take the form of efficient or opportunistic behavior (Chhabra, 2016). Based on the phenomena that occur in the practice of EM in the Kalla Group, it is more directed to the application of Efficient EM. with the Accrual Basis recognition method. In addition to the accrual model providing fairness values, some weaknesses have the opportunity to create opportunistic actions. Managers who choose to plan bonuses will tend to choose accounting methods that increase earnings in the current period. Research on earnings management suggests that management compensation positively affects earnings management(Sofia & Murwaningsari, 2019). Managers will act opportunistically to practice earnings management to get high

bonuses. The concept of accrual can be interpreted more deeply in Al-Baqarah Quran sura 2 verse 282, which means:

“O you who believe, when you do mu'amalah not in cash for a specified time, you shall write it down. And let a scribe among you write it down correctly. And let not the scribe refuse to write it as Allah has taught it, let him write, and let the debtor dictate (what will be written it), and let him fear Allah his Lord, and let him not reduce the least of his debt. If a debtor is a person who is weak in mind or weak (his condition) or he is not able to dictate, then his guardian should dictate honestly. And bear witness with two witnesses from the men (among you). If there are not two men, then (maybe) one man and two women from among the witnesses you are pleased with, so that if one forgets, then one reminds him. Let not the witnesses refuse (to testify) when they are called, and do not get tired of writing the debt, whether small or large, until the deadline to pay it. That is more just in the sight of Allah and more steadfast in testimony and nearer to not (raise) your doubt. (Write your transaction), unless the transaction is a cash trade you make between you, there is no sin for you (if) you do not write it. And bear witness when you trade; don't let writers and witnesses make it difficult for each other. If you do (that), then it is indeed wickedness for you. And keep your duty to Allah. God teaches you; Allah is Aware of all things.”

Earnings management can arise from the problem of information asymmetry and agency conflict. This information asymmetry condition will exist if equity ownership is separate from the company's operations and managers have an advantage over information over shareholders (Huang et al., 2013; Small et al., 2015). Agency theory is concerned with solving two problems between the principal: 1) the different desires or goals of the two parties (principal and agent), 2) the problem of risk-sharing. Principals and agents have their views in determining risk choices, leading to different ways of solving the problems they face. The literature review used as a reference in this research is several studies related to efficient EM. For example, in study by Wijaya (2017) yang menyatakan bahwa EM menyebabkan investor yang menganalisis suatu perusahaan dengan analisis fundamental akan mengalami mislead dan akan berdampak terhadap Nilai Perusahaan. Tandry et al. (2014); Chen & Hung (2021) proves that efficient EM has a positive relationship to firm value, so that the presence of efficient EM will increase the value of a company.

On the other hand, Priantinah (2016) explained that the good side of EM could be viewed from the point of view of efficient contracts in financial reporting. In the perspective of Positive Accounting Theory, the standpoint of efficient contracts explains that the level of EM can be considered good because it can increase contract efficiency. Then added by Abdullah & Ainun (2017) shows that EM Proxy affects Future Profitability. From an Islamic perspective, the study of EM has been explained by Azouzi et al. (2015), which shows that the solution in earnings management is if the intentions (Niyah) of the managers can be purified through ethics (Akhlaq). It is hoped that they will apply the highest possible effort and knowledge (Ijtihad) to ensure the stakeholders' interests (Maslahah). Then strengthened in the study of Putra & Widyani (2019) with an Islamic perspective explains that EM is an act of dhazalim, contrary to the value of honesty (Siddiq), contrary to values, and contrary to halal (halal thayyiban). Therefore, this study also concludes that managers can create a good performance with the expected profit pattern based on the value of professionalism in accordance with Islamic sharia (akhlakul karimah) to comply with Islamic sharia principles.

Method

The location of this research is in the city of Makassar, where most of the data sources in the Makassar area are at the Head Office within the business scope of the Kalla Group which will be carried out for 3 (three) months. This type of research is qualitative research, descriptive qualitative research. The sampling procedure of quantitative research informants was carried out by purposive sampling. Informants and types of information collected that will be the source of data in this study are people who are directly involved in accounting practices in the Kalla Group business, including:

1. Two Chief Financial Officers (CFOs) from the OTO and DEVCON groups. The CFO (Chief Finance Officer) was chosen to ensure that the relevant parties have experience and have served in the Kalla Group for a long time. This position is in the decision-maker position regarding the financial policies carried out by companies within the Kalla Group. The types of information obtained from this informant are:
 - Description of EM efficient treatment in the Kalla group
 - How is the perspective of EM efficient from the standpoint of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group.
 - How is the construction of EM efficient in the Kalla group.

2. Finance Division Head (FDH) as many as two people from KallaAspal and PT. BarugaAsrinusa is also part of the Kalla Group. The Finance Division Head was chosen as an informant to provide an alternative perspective in research to find accounting practices related to efficient EM in Kalla Group companies. The types of information obtained from this informant are:
 - An overview of EM efficiency in the perspective of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group.
 - How is the form and construction of EM efficient in the perspective of Islamic ethics in the KallaGroup.
3. There are two Accounting Managers at Kalla Group from the Finance Operation Division Head of Kalla DEVCON and the Corporate Finance Accounting & Tax Division Head. The Accounting Manager also became an informant in this study to add information related to efficient EM practices in companies within the Kalla Group. The types of information obtained from this informant are:
 - An overview of EM efficiency in the perspective of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group.
 - The views of accountants in the Kalla Group Regarding the construction of an EM efficient general picture in an Islamic perspective.

The informants who are the sources of information in this study are part of the strategic positions within the Kalla Group company. There are 2 (two) main groups that are directly under the management of Kalla Group, namely GO Kalla OTO and GO KallaDevcon. GO Kalla OTO is an SBU operation group engaged in the automotive sector, and GO KallaDevcon is an SBU operation group involved in development and construction. The two main operating groups can represent the Kalla Group business group and implement the values that are built and run and form the best business process. Business processes, one of which is information systems and accounting practices, presented later, are expected to provide a specific explanation regarding the efficient implementation of EM in the Kalla Group. The data collection technique in this study was carried out utilizing Focus Group Discussion (FGD). FGDs were conducted to obtain initial information as an overview of the EM process and identify and ascertain the informants to be interviewed.

Results and Discussion

EM Treatment at Kalla Group

1. Efficient EM Kalla Group Actualization

There are 2 (two) main GO SBUs of Kalla Group consisting of 10 business units directly controlled by management who can describe EM practices and financial reporting management. The results of interviews with the Corporate Finance Accounting & Tax Division Head think that:

"Simply put, profit management in an opportunist context is that of taking advantage of the situation to gain an advantage. And I think both ethically and corporately disagree. Because it would violate the rules in general, especially when discussing religion. Meanwhile, when talking about efficient EM. We are looking ahead about managing the company's business (finance) leading to an efficient level. Efficient can be interpreted as mutual understanding between owners and employees in carrying out company activities so that the obligations of agents and principals continue to run. In the company's perspective, external is a partner where under certain conditions, such as taxation. In this Covid condition, external parties and related companies must be able to understand each other about the company's condition so that there is a meeting point (solution) in every problem."

The informant from the Finance Department Head of PT BarugaAsrinusa further explained that: *"Yes, the practice of EM efficiency is applied in the Kalla Group because the owner is part of the company over time the revenue aspect is the most prominent thing."*

Practice efficient EM as a signaling mechanism to facilitate efficient communication between managers and information users. Another thing is also proven that some of the roles of the owner act as agents, meaning that it can make it easier for contracts to be carried out efficiently. The signals provided through the EM are used to increase the value relevance of financial reporting and strengthen investors' ability to predict company performance. Owners or investors want managers to do efficient earnings management for two reasons: (1). Managers can reduce the cost of capital through a more even and predictable flow of profits. (2). A more stable profit stream affects potential investors' perceptions of a better firm value. EM efficiency in the Kalla Group is characterized by an agreement between the agent and the principal for corporate purposes. The EM practice in the Kalla group was found to be efficient in implementing EM. The data and interview results illustrate that the Kalla Group takes policies in contract selection, measurement, valuation, and recognition or accounting policies

based on mutual agreement between agents and principals. Collective agreements are made for the company's purpose to maximize efficiency contracts and company utility. The financial data can be presented in the last 5 (five) years 2015-2019, as follows in table 1.

Table 1. Revenue and Strategic Net Profit of Kalla Group Business Units (SBUs) 2015-2019

No	Years	Income	Net Profit
1	2015	6.162.076.694.154,-	337.195.535.245,-
2	2016	5.763.768.610.362,-	250.623.340.844,-
3	2017	5.452.651.787.460,-	118.065.067.526,-
4	2018	6.053.996.890.156,-	169.213.931.117,-
5	2019	6.462.211.335.891,-	165.990.210.945,-

On the other hand, the results of interviews with Informants from Devcon's CFO explained that:

"EM practice is carried out based on the needs of financial reporting and the needs of the Kalla Group itself. Also, based on the needs of stakeholders. This interest must be accommodated so that the sustainability of the company continues to run, including employee salaries, company owners and others."

Furthermore, the informant from CFO Kalla OTO explained:

"If we look at the process, from the beginning of the year there was a target set which became the management's commitment which of course refers to how the operational activities are going well so that the agreed profit can be achieved. Therefore, it can be said that the Kalla Group has implemented this."

Kalla Group's Efficient EM practice is carried out following the needs of stakeholders and the applicable principles to ensure the company's going concerned. Earnings management has become a management commitment between managers and owners in annual targets to efficient contracts to achieve operational targets. Efficient arrangements assume that earnings management can be used to facilitate internal control and decision-making. Efficient EM is carried out to anticipate the transfer of welfare between the parties involved in the contract. Efficient contracts are designed by considering the principal's and lenders' expectations of the manager's opportunistic behavior and incorporating the manager's opportunistic behavior's anticipated impact into the contract. Thus only the manager's opportunism is not expected, which is an inefficient action. In this condition, earnings management can be used as a tool for managers to strengthen contract efficiency. EM Kalla Group's treatment of efficiency describes phenomena and practices carried out following an efficient contract and applicable standards. Based on the results of interviews with informants from the Finance Operations Division Head, KallaDevcon stated that:

"It should be done properly, should not make a deviant report, make it as it is and don't deviate. If there is a request from anyone, it depends on what purpose. However, in principle, the report is not too distorted. In the Kalla Group itself, I can honestly say it was done. When it decreases (profit) and vice versa."

An informant from the Finance Department Head KallaAspal also expressed his view that:

"Based on the current accounting policies and practices, Kalla Group applies the practice of Efficient EM because some forms of measurement and recognition are carried out based on the considerations and policies of the owners and management of the company. Another uniqueness seen in the Kalla Group is that the owner/principal partially acts as an agent or controller in the company's operations. Those who practice Efficient EM are the managers and some agreements with the owners. Efficient EM is carried out to accommodate several internal interests such as performance achievement/KPI and external interests such as banking, taxation, and project tenders. Efficient EM practice is carried out every month and year. The practice of Efficient EM at SBU was initially carried out based on generally accepted accounting principles. Still, with its development, company owners have many demands and interests to continue to exist and develop. Several interests, such as achieving targets/KPIs and banking and taxation, are accommodated through Efficient EM practices. In addition to professional considerations that are often carried out, they are also heavily dominated by external interests. An example of Efficient EM that is carried out is the selection of measurement and recognition methods so that they reflect conditions that are following market or external needs."

From the interview results, it can be interpreted that the implementation of Efficient EM at the Kalla Group is implemented by considering the company's needs both in terms of internal performance appraisal and external interests. However, all forms of action are still based on the applicable rules. Efficient EM is carried out in all business lines of the Kalla Group and maintains behavior not to expect opportunistic actions. The practice of Efficient EM is proven by the agent and principal agreeing for the company's interest to run an efficient contract. Efficient contracts can produce high performance and profits following the expectations of agents and principals. Another uniqueness is that some of the owners act as agents because it is based on the Kalla Group is a family company that, apart from being filled by generations of owners and professionals.

2. Accrual and Expected Utility

The results of interviews with informants from the Finance Operations Division Head KallaDevcon stated that:

"In practice, so far, there have been those who have carried out the Cash Basis and Accrual basis because they did not manipulate the report, but the motive was not there. There must be no personal interest that can damage the company. However, there may still be 1 or 2 that are deviant but still in a reasonable state."

Then the informant from the Corporate Finance Accounting & Tax Division Head added:

"The Kalla group applies the accrual bookkeeping technique, but the obstacle is how to determine when the accrual point occurs because there are many different understandings from marketing and finance parties. From a marketing point of view, when there is a commitment between the seller and the buyer, on the other hand, the finance side still refers to the SAK that applies when acknowledging the sale, relying on two main principles, namely the transfer of rights and obligations between the two parties. The second is that the customer has complete its obligations. If it is associated with cash, it means that the customer has paid off, then if it is related to credit, it means that there are legal aspects that show the customer's commitment to pay at a certain time."

Then the informant from the Finance Department Head KallaAspal added the following:

"Efficient EM practice technique used is the basic accrual system consisting of discretionary accruals and non-discretionary accruals. The dominant factor is discretionary accruals because it is influenced by management policies, meaning that managers intervene in financial reporting. Some forms of utility expectations that are usually carried out, such as: achieving targets/KPIs, are carried out with recognition techniques for both income and costs, taking advantage of government incentives, both prices, and taxes, and ending the term of office or changing positions by using recognition techniques with good performance."

Applicable accounting standards have applied the accrual aspect of the Kalla Group. The most crucial thing in operations is to produce accurate operational performance information as a basis for evaluation and performance appraisal. Earnings management can be measured through discretionary accruals. Technically, the recognition and estimation are still within reasonable limits in practice at the Kalla Group.

In Surah Al-Baqarah: 282, it is explicitly explained that if you do mu'amalah which is not done in cash for a specified time, you should write it down. This means that the concept of accrual has been stipulated in the Qur'an before being regulated in standards or PSAK. It is also stated in total that a writer among you should write it correctly. This means that agents or managers who are responsible for bookkeeping in a company want to put forward ethical principles and values to be consistent with the applicable rules. The accrual concept is the basis for the balance between rights and obligations in the matching concept principle. Another thing that was revealed was that transaction inflation should not be carried out, and accruals must be carried out somewhat by the Chief Finance Officer Kalla OTO informant who stated that:

"Jusuf Kalla (founder of the Kalla Group) emphasized that the calculation of economic indicators in the real sector essentially avoids the ballooning of transactions. So the accrual practice is carried out fairly following the actual conditions."

Expected utility and the use of the accrual method in the presentation of financial statements in the Kalla group, especially related to the motives for several actions, such as bonuses and others. The results of the interview with the Corporate Finance Accounting & Tax Division Head stated that:

"The accrual aspect of the Kalla Group has been applied following applicable accounting standards. The most important thing in operations is to produce real operational performance information as a basis for evaluation and performance appraisal. Earnings management can be measured through discretionary accruals. Technically, the recognition and estimation are still within reasonable limits in practice at the Kalla Group."

Then the informant from the Finance Department Head KallaAspal added the following:

"At Kalla Group, what is more, dominant is for the interests of external parties. We can see the audit reports, although some are related to internal interests (e.g., rewards or bonuses)."

Chief Finance Officer Kalla DEVCON also explained that:

"We have to be fair, especially regarding bonuses. It may be related to this, for example, but it still has to be coordinated. This bonus is not something that just happens, but we still see its urgency and materiality. For example, profit is not achieved by 0.01 or only a little, and bonuses are not given because of a target problem. This should not be something that deviates if it can be conditioned so that the bonus is still given."

In addition, Chief Finance Officer Kalla OTO Kasim confirmed that:

"Here, there is an element of management policy related to the importance of presenting the information. However, there is value for the Kalla road; the company benefits the owner and the community. Management remains committed to providing useful financial information, for example, for tax reporting obligations. To motivate employees, rewards for achievement are considered. The basis is the achievement of employee performance through key performance indicators (KPI). So the practice of EM related to this is still within reasonable limits."

Based on the interview results, it can be interpreted that the implementation of the accrual method and based on the utility aspect at Kalla Group remains in a clear corridor and suppresses opportunist practices. This means that Kalla Group strives for all forms of financial statements to be presented based on applicable principles and rules. Furthermore, the business processes run by the Kalla Group run with Kalla Value which are very thick with Islamic values. Not only the interests of the company, but also the interests of the owners, employees, society and the state.

3. Asymmetric Information Agents and Principals of Kalla Group

Information asymmetry of financial statement information within the Kalla Group can be explained based on data from several parties involved in the business within the company. The results of interviews with informants from the Finance Department Head of PT BarugaAsrinusa explained:

"We will look at it from the company's point of view first because from the employee's point of view. It is unlikely to happen. Regarding the engineering action, I think it happened only for the company's interests. Employees or management, whatever their attitude, whatever their behavior, tend to see it from the point of view of the company's interests. This means that if we talk about attitudes or behavior, there are values called Jalan Kalla, which are still being socialized to this day. As an employee, that is what guides attitudes and behavior as a guide and code of ethics. So if in the end there is an EM practice, it will all remain on the path that has been determined by the owner of the company, not purely the desire of the company, although there are still some information asymmetry."

Furthermore, an informant from the Finance Department Head of PT BarugaAsrinusa explained that:

"There is a unique condition in the Kalla Group that the owner is part of the management. This can be called an inherent situation in Kalla Group companies. This means that the wishes or policies of the owner are powerful because of the dual status. If we want it better, the agent theory in the Kalla group does not apply; ownership is legally separate, but de facto is not separate. So it is difficult to determine"

which is the decision of the owner and which is the decision of the management because of their dual status."

An informant from the Finance Operations Division Head, KallaDevcon, also explained that:

"Not because of his religion, but because of the integrity that can maintain in providing good financial statement information." In addition, according to him: "Now, in the Kalla Group, there is already a sound system, for example, the Oracle System. That is what must ensure that there are no deviations. The average closed company still tends to deviate, and there is information asymmetry. I have always wanted only one type of financial report. But no matter how good the system is, the one who runs it (humans) is not good. That will determine the result. The basis for excellent and correct financial statements is ethics, especially in the Islamic religion."

The interview results explained that the relationship between the manager (agent) and the owner (principal) in the disclosure of information in the Kalla Group business was considered to still refer to the company's interests. In practice, Asymmetric Information still exists, but it tries to be suppressed for the common good, and the company's going concerned. Conflicts also often occur because companies that use a concentrated ownership structure put their families in management, making it easy to control management policies in obtaining personal benefits for management. Efficient earnings management carried out by the administration also aims to control or monitor the company's internal so that managers can choose accounting policies that are not aimed at maximizing personal interests. Managers often manipulate the numbers in financial statements, which impacts misleading investors and even owners in analyzing a company's performance. Efficient EM practice aims to increase information about earnings, communicate private information within the company and reduce asymmetric information. The owner's existence in the company structure or several principals acting as agents will suppress opportunistic practices. The results of the interview with the Chief Finance Officer of Kalla OTO also explained that:

"The Kalla group can be said as a family company. Of course, the owner is still the executor. So that the agency and principal factors are almost fused. To maintain essential and valid information, generally accepted accounting principles are applied."

Based on the results of interviews related to asymmetric information, it can be interpreted that there is something unique in the Kalla Group. The agent and principal agree and are committed to the common interest of the company's goals. The implementation of efficient contracts and eliminating opportunistic practices illustrate the effort to minimize conflicts of interest. The company is a family company, and of course, the owner is also the executor. So that the agency and principal factors are almost said to be fused. The presentation of financial statements is still carried out based on a code of ethics that applies both internally and externally. In addition, Kalla Group already has a system that integrates all SBUs in one form of financial statements. However, there may still be some things that need to be maximized so that the objectives of presenting financial statements can be achieved.

4. EM Kalla Group's Efficient Treatment

Efficient EM in the Kalla Group can be described as 3 (three) leading indicators that become full attention in maximizing the company's utility. These indicators consist of bonus plans, debt covenants, and political costs, which are carried out by agreement between the agent and the principal involved. Efficient EM is closely related to contracting theory, which can be anticipated with contracts that can be negotiated through efficient contracts expected to reduce costs. The Debt Covenant is carried out by not violating the debt agreement contract, resulting in prices for the company. Political Costs in the implementation are usually for large companies with high political costs; managers will prefer accounting methods that defer profits. Therefore, it is necessary to choose an accounting method that does not rely on the interests of the agent or principal. The Efficient EM implementation model can be described as follows:

Figure 1. Kalla Group's Efficient EM Model

Several views of financial managers at Kalla Group also convey the same thing. Efficient EM's action is not a motive that aims to select an impartial accounting method for particular interests in communicating the company's financial condition. Efficient EM within the Kalla Group is carried out with the agreement of the agent and principal to choose an efficient contract for the company's scope and its relations with external parties. Efficient EM actions are carried out with caution and following the applicable corridors and rules, both rules relating to internal companies and regulations related to the government (e.g., corporate tax reporting).

Reflection on Islamic Ethics in Efficient EM Practices

1. The existence of An Islamic Manager (Agent) Kalla Group

Ethics in Islam encourages humans to bring peace, honesty, and justice. The work ethic in Islam also teaches that humans in carrying out their work are carried out honestly and trustworthy (not taking something that is not their right, not cheating, being objective in judging) and not violating sharia principles. The Kalla Group, which also operates Efficient EM, also adheres to regulations and ethics that are carried out following the values that have been firmly held since the company's inception. In practice, the Kalla Group is unique in its management structure. The results of an interview with the Finance Department Head of PT BarugaAsrinusa stated that:

"Kalla group's financial managers are Muslim and of course very obedient to Islamic rules and ethics as well as the values built by the founders of Kalla Group, the most important behavior in terms of behavior, morals in EM practice."

Informant Finance Department Head PT BarugaAsrinusa further stated that:

"As a financial person, of course referring to behavior, morals and professional standards also refers to PSAK. Also, at KG, the Kalla Management System (RKMS) House is the reference. Of course, we must refer to these two things, externally there is PSAK, and internally, we follow the RumahKalla Management System (starting from the value, financial and other aspects). Then there are times when there are bound to be conflicts in the application, policies, and directives, both of which will clash with existing standards. But whatever happens, to test it, we will face an audit. This auditor will later correct what I think will end there. The context is different again if we talk about managerial reports for internal consumption, which are made according to needs which of course have different interests (e.g., financial efficiency analysis)".

Then according to the informant from the Corporate Finance Accounting & Tax Division Head explained that:

"From a personal point of view, what I highlight is that the company clearly states that work is worship (company philosophical values) to the company's business strategy. The company has made efforts to synchronize Islamic values into the company culture so that it can be used as ijtihad or individual KPI."

Informants who came from informants from the Finance Operations Division Head KallaDevcon also stated that:

"As an Islamic manager in the Kalla group, of course, he is powerful with straight morals and intentions in starting activities that are strengthened by Kalla's values and the Kalla House Management System (RKMS), which is a guideline and compliance with the code of ethics."

An informant from the Chief Finance Officer of Kalla DEVCON also expressed his opinion that:

"We start from Kalla's values, namely religious work, for example, friends in Finance & Accounting, all return to their values and morals. The Kalla Group has also been regulated by using ERP and the RumaKalla Management System (RKMS), which are systematic from transactions to the publication of

financial statements; this is one of the efforts to minimize misstatements of financial statements. In integrity, the numbers recorded should be based on reasonable evidence."

An informant from the Chief Finance Officer of Kalla OTO also added that:

"In terms of values, this is the founder's appreciation so that in implementing the policy, the context of worship is the patron or measure by paying attention to the intentions and principles of religious values in presenting the output of financial statements following appropriate conditions. "Yes, we as Kalla people are indeed the majority who I am a Muslim and I, as a manager in an Islamic position, prioritizes Islamic values and morals. We realize that nature is human nature about goodness which greatly determines morals that can distinguish between good and evil, thus giving birth to good intentions to give birth to maximum effort to carry out the duties of mandates assigned by the owner. Apart from this, we are also greatly influenced by management interventions and policies so that sometimes we shift from the practice of non-discretionary accruals.

Managers or agents of the Kalla Group, who are commonly called Islamic Managers, are strongly shaped by Kalla's values (corporate values) and adherence to the Kalla House Management System (RKMS). RKMS is a reference in managing the company, starting from building a shared vision of the company culture, understanding and practicing company values. It is necessary to choose a role model and change agents who will become corporate culture ambassadors. Leaders and Culture Champions need to create comprehensive, consistent, disciplined programs and involve all employees. Dissemination of values related to communication and socialization. To build, understand and ensure that practices following core values are maintained, all corporate culture programs need to be in line and harmony with the existing system. The goal is to align the current system with the company's core values.

Management plays a role in instructing the Kalla House Management System RKMS as a policy that the entire Kalla Group must obey. Ensure that procedures are socialized to all employees in their respective business units, ensure that the internalization of Kalla Group's values refers to the approved guidelines. Efficient EM reasonably to provide stakeholders within the Maslahah scope. Therefore, it is essential to present Islamic ethics with solid support from the early teachings. They were presenting several original concepts of Islamic ethics in the form of prophetic messages and instructions of the Prophet Muhammad, namely Iman (faith), Niyah (intention), Amanah (Amanah), and 'Adalah (justice). This shows that an essential point in measuring employee ethics must be ethical in all situations that provide a multiplier effect in the company's management and have the potential as an educational function for employees.

From the results of interviews related to Efficient EM based on an Islamic perspective at the Kalla Group, it can be interpreted that managers (agents) are Islamic managers and certainly prioritize aspects of good behavior and morals. The most critical behavior in presenting financial statements has the primary patron, namely financial accounting standards or regulations in producing applicable financial statements. However, there is a difference between Kalla Group and other companies, namely Kalla Value and Islamic Value. Kalla's values are based on the typical Bugis-Makassar culture. In contrast, Islamic values are based on the Qur'an and Hadith as well as other provisions in religion so that the output of financial statements is full of accountability and is very careful in its presentation.

2. Behavior Manager (Agent) Kalla Group

From the interviews with financial managers within the Kalla Group company, it was revealed that the existence of values and the strength of religious teachings (Islam) could then maintain the company's sustainability. Although there is a slight shift, it remains a priority in building a better company. The results of the interview with the informant of the Finance Operations Division Head, KallaDevcon, explained the behavior of agents within the company as follows:

"This Kalla has a value called the Kalla value, which its founder built. However, in terms of implementation, I think it was stronger before than now. Although often communicated, but the implementation has not gone well. Business is not just profit, but there is worship value in it."

An informant from the Finance Department Head KallaAspal revealed that:

"The behavior of the managers (agents) refers to ethics as a Muslim and of course following the values built by the Kalla Group, namely work of worship. These values become the basis for staying on the correct rail or corridor or according to the rules."

Informants from Chief Finance Officer Kalla DEVCON also revealed that:

"The behavior of Kalla Group managers' behavior must refer to Kalla's values such as worship, customer appreciation, faster the better, and being active together. These values can maintain conduct and ethics in doing business following Islamic values.

Meanwhile, according to the informant, Chief Finance Officer Kalla OTO revealed that:

"The behavior of Kalla people certainly refers to the values instilled by its founder. The period of Hadji Kalla (founder of the Kalla Group) was more in worship work. He became known as a merchant of the mosque. Mrs. Athirah (Hadji Kalla's wife) relates to marketing values emphasizing a conscientious approach that raises customer appreciation. Then continued Mr. Jusuf Kalla (son and pioneer of Kalla Group Becoming Modern) using his economics approach, the sooner, the better. Then in the period of Mrs. Fatimah Kalla (Jusuf Kalla's wife), a value called being active together concerning decision-making involving bottom-up emerged, meaning that decision values pay attention to the value of deliberation and spirituality."

Kalla's values (corporate values) are the primary basis for all Kalla people to carry out activities according to the rules and based on Islamic values. The corporate values that were built consisted of work of worship initiated by Mr. Hadji Kalla, customer appreciation by Mrs. HajjaAthirah, the sooner, the better by Mr. Jusuf Kalla, and Active Together by Mrs. Fatimah Kalla. The existence of statements from several informants as above can reveal the behavior of agents who are managers who are Muslim. In principle, they are obliged to behave in Islam. A condition is understood that there are demands or shifts in the modern era, but the priority is to maintain business values and ethics. Kalla Group's corporate values are a reflection of the agent's behavior in implementing Efficient EM. Efficient EM practices are a reference to maintain values and avoid opportunistic practices. These are the basis for the continuity and sustainability of the company in the long term.

3. Kalla Group's Islamic Ethical Practices

Five philosophical axioms form the Islamic ethical system: (1) Oneness, namely integration between all areas of life; religious, economic, and socio-political-cultural, as well as the unity between business activities with morality and seeking the pleasure of Allah; (2) Balance, namely the human ability to create balance/moderation in life activities, for example, an attitude not to be stingy nor extravagant towards others; (3) Free will, that is, humans in this world are given free will by Allah in their every action to achieve their life goals, namely to spread mercy to the whole world; (4) Responsibility, namely humans in carrying out every action in this world will have consequences for being responsible for every action that has been carried out; (5) Virtue, namely the willingness of humans to always do good for themselves and others. More specifically, regarding Islamic ethics in accounting, there are 9 (nine) ethical provisions on the accounting function in Islam, including (1) Reported correctly; (2) Fast reporting, namely reporting every transaction data according to the period in which it occurs; (3) Made by an expert (accountant); (4) Bright, clear, firm and informative; (5) Contains comprehensive information; (6) Information is addressed to all parties involved horizontally and vertically; (7) Detailed and thorough; (8) No manipulation occurs; (9) Done continuously (not negligent). Islamic ethics views that every business activity must rely on its spirit to Islamic ethics. The results of the interview with the Finance Department Head KallaAspal said that:

"Islamic ethics is very much in line with and as the basis for determining the values applied in the Kalla Group. The values of the Kalla group that the founders and their generations sparked include; Worship work by Mr. H. Kalla, Customer Appreciation by Mrs. Hj. Athirah, The sooner, the better by Mr. H. Jusuf Kalla, and Active Together by Mrs. Hj. Fatima Kalla. These values are inherent and taught to all employees to be applied and implemented in the company's business processes in a sustainable manner."

KallaDevcon's Finance Operations Division Head also revealed that:

"The Islamic Work Ethics within the Kalla Group can be translated into the values instilled by the founders of the Kalla group, such as Work of Worship, Customer Appreciation, Better Faster, and Active Together. This value is embodied in all of Kalla's people."

Several things that strengthen the practice of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group are when asked about the business character of Hadji Kalla. The nature of Hadji Kalla's business is strictly sharia. For him, running a

company must be following sharia. It is forbidden for him to carry out transactions that involve things that are prohibited by sharia. Aspects of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group are highly reflected in the founders' values (corporate values). This is also expressed in the view of the Chief Finance Officer of Kalla OTO that:

"Of course, one fundamental thing is to build the spirit instilled by the founders, especially in terms of maintaining value even though there are external and internal related profit management interests. But keep in mind that this is related to responsibilities in this world and the hereafter. Therefore, the intention and sincerity in presenting information must maintain those values. The point is not to leave the policies (Spiritual and Cultural) instilled by the founders so that the founder's character is still manifested in the company's body."

The above statement shows that the ethics built within the Kalla Group company are not only related to ethics that are only generally accepted. However, there is a metaphysical relationship, followed by inherent cultural values. So that the unification of spiritual and cultural values provides a spirit for the sustainability of the company's business. The description of the phenomenon and a brief history of Hadji Kalla's journey illustrates that the Kalla Group is firm with its founder's values (Corporate Value). These values are continuously maintained and embodied by all Kalla people. Strong values with Islamic ethical principles become a strong foundation in maintaining consistency in business activities and decisions. Islamic ethics and professional ethics serve as guidelines for creating and maintaining the values instilled in the Kalla Group.

Kalla's Convergence of Values

Figure 2. Convergence of Kalla Group's Values

4. Form Efficient EM Islamic Ethical Perspective Kalla Group

Kalla Group's efficient EM practice is one of the goals to reduce the existence of asymmetric information and opportunistic practices. The agreement between the agent and the principal becomes a commitment to achieve the company's goals or interests and targets. The results of the interview with the Finance Department Head of PT BarugaAsrinusa stated that:

"When it comes to external reports, of course, it has been tested and evaluated. Of course, if we borrow the word 'engineering,' it is almost non-existent because the report is more for external purposes. It's different if we talk about internal reports because the owner and top management are difficult to separate, but even then, it still refers to the company's interests. The most important note is that external audit will also not dare to issue reports that are not appropriate because it will have an impact on the practice license so that the reports that have been issued are reports that have been tested for validity."

The results of an interview with the Finance Department Head of PT BarugaAsrinusa stated that:

"I think we already know that there are external rules that we must obey, and there are internal rules. Then internally, the most emphasized is the application of values. For example, every employee must follow the induction of new employees who are given the understanding to understand Kalla's values. Of course, if we talk about values, we will discuss culture, then if we talk about culture, we need role models or role models as examples of different times with different leaders. But the most important thing right now is when we talk about the value of how it becomes a culture, and when we talk about culture, of course, we need the role of a leader. Kalla Group is also very thick with Islamic values, such as integrity, accountability, and professionalism".

Finance Operations Division Head KallaDevcon added that:

"Wherever we work, we must start from the intention that I want to work to carry out the mandate so that what is done is carried out to carry out the mandate. If not, that's what causes the deviation because it is not based on that value. Religiously, with the existence of a mandate, someone who runs well, even if there is a code of ethics or not, will believe that Allah SWT supervises him. Let alone practice, in mind alone will not occur because he feels supervised by Allah SWT. I think I agree, but some may not have been given the ability and strength to live. This is a matter of guidance where monotheism upholds the truth because it is a strength given by Allah SWT. If there is no strong effort, then the trust will be difficult to carry out. In addition to ethical principles, it is also revealed in professional ethics for Kalla Group accountants who obey and reflect competence, objectivity, and integrity."

Meanwhile, according to the Corporate Finance Accounting & Tax Division Head stated that:

"The size of the level of Islamic values varies from person to person. So sometimes someone says it's running, but someone says it hasn't. But I can say that the company owner has dared to say that the company's philosophy is rooted in Islamic teachings. However, the Kalla Group has dared to include the values of religious teachings in its philosophy so that they are used as performance indicators. Philosophically, religious values already exist in the Kalla Group, which is the basis for managers carrying out work activities at the Kalla Group. The root of ethics is religion; every moral principle then its foundation is Islam. That is the measure of every manager in applying the teachings of his religion. Professional professionalism is related to the professional ethics of accountants, morality, and independence. The foundation is back to religion. There are basic values about good and bad values that must be understood. If the understanding is good, then the ethics of an accountant will be good."

Behavior to guard against fraudulent practices both in buying and selling and in financial reporting violates Islamic ethics and values. This prohibition is clearly stated in the word of Allah SWT in QS. Al Muthaffifin verses 1-6 which means

"Big misfortune for those who cheat (i.e.) people who when they receive a dose from someone else they ask for it to be filled, and when they measure or weigh for someone else, they reduce it. These people do not think that they will be resurrected, on a great day, (i.e.) the day (when) humankind will stand before the Lord of the worlds."

In another verse, Allah SWT mentions that fulfilling the applicable provisions and regulations is more important and has better benefits in a company's business in QS. Al Isra Verse 35 which means:

"And complete the measure when you measure and weigh it with the right balance. That is more important (for you) and better as a result".

Kalla Group's perspective in implementing efficient earnings management based on Islamic ethics. The results of the interview with the Chief Finance Officer of Kalla OTO confirmed that Efficient EM in the Islamic perspective at Kalla Group was revealed as follows:

"Obviously during the late period. Hadji Kalla is more about the context of worship work. He became known as a merchant of the mosque. Then continued by his son (Mr. Jusuf Kalla) using his scientific approach (economics) but still based on the values brought by his parents. Then in the period of Mrs. Fatimah Kalla, a value emerged called being active together concerning decision making involving bottom-up, meaning that decision values pay attention to the value of deliberation and spirituality. The late Mrs. Athirah itself deals with marketing values that emphasize a conscientious approach that

raises customer appreciation. All of these values are encapsulated in 'Jalan Kalla', which are the basis for the company in carrying out its activities by upholding the principles of trust and truth. Kalla Group is very focused on paying attention to the accounting field. This is proven through the collaboration of the Kalla Group with the Indonesian Institute of Accountants. This shows professionalism, competence, and objective as well as increases accounting knowledge for financial managers. However, this is accompanied by a combination of religious beliefs and awareness, then added with professionalism in accounting. so that it is expected that every decision making is based on accounting financial statement information based on it."

KallaAspal's Finance Department Head revealed that:

"Ethical principles/behaviors that form the basis of the Kalla group's corporate values, such as monotheism, justice, freedom, responsibility, and truth. It can also be translated into a professional code of ethics such as; professional behavior, responsibility, competence, objective, legitimacy, and integrity. In addition to the principles and code of professional ethics, it is also strengthened by Islamic values that the Kalla group's people carry out. This can change the behavior of efficient EM practices, which in implementation are more dominant in accommodating management interventions and certain interests in the financial reporting process. The concept of Islamic ethics will change perspectives and decisions that can ensure the continuity of Islamic companies without harming certain parties".

Islamic ethics and values are the guidelines for maintaining the behavior of each agent and principal in every company's business activities within the Kalla Group. Obedience to the religion of Allah SWT and Islamic values that can maintain consistency in the practice of Efficient EM within the Kalla Group. The principles of Islamic ethics and revealed in professional ethics strengthen the behavior and morals of every Kalla person. The findings to each actor or agent generally explain that the management of financial statements at the Kalla Group is carried out with full responsibility based on generally accepted rules. However, what is noted from the interviews shows an effect resulting from the unification of local wisdom, values adopted by the company, ethics, and values that exist in religious teachings (Islam). One thing that was revealed in the interview was the principle of monotheism, balance, freedom, responsibility, and truth. This principle is reflected in the ethical behavior of the accountant or manager who has a mandate in each business unit which becomes the culture within the company. Kalla Values and Islamic values later became a rule that Kalla People and Management should carry out. In addition to Islamic ethics, it is also revealed in professional ethics such as professionalism, encouragement of belief, competence, objectivity, legitimacy, and trust. It is this ethical principle that minimizes the risks of irregularities in presenting financial statements. Efficient EM shows that the urgency of the practices carried out by the company (Kalla Group) is in the interests of the company and its stakeholders by staying on track and following generally accepted rules. The relevant parties can account for practices that promote efficient contracts.

EM Efficient Construction Formulation

1. EM Kalla Group's Efficient Construction Formulation

Attempts to reconstruct Efficient EM in a good direction for the company's sustainability is not easy, especially regarding the religious values in it. Several views on efficient earnings management from interviews related to efforts to construct efficient earnings management models to make them valid and benefit the company. The interviews with informants revealed that the construction carried out in the practice of efficient EM needs to be made several efforts to make it ideal and bring benefits. The first is to keep in mind generally accepted financial reporting standards. Then to avoid engineering efforts in the presentation of financial statements, noble values are needed in the corporate culture. This is reflected in the Kalla Value run by the Kalla Group, one of its values is worship, customer appreciation, the sooner, the better, and being active together. The implementation of these values plays a vital role in maintaining the consistency of Efficient EM practice. Furthermore, so that the management of financial reporting information can have a beneficial impact (profit masalah) for the company, efforts are needed to maintain spiritual (religious) values based on faith, holiness, and honesty. An Islamic ethical perspective is a suitable construction to change the practice of Efficient EM to be stronger, guaranteeing the benefit and going concerned of the company.

In addition to the main principles of Islamic ethics, it is also revealed in professional ethics as an accountant, which are the basis, obligations, and guidelines for maintaining professionalism. The ethics and values that are carried out will be the basis for maintaining the trust or trust of the principal or owner. Kalla Group, which Islamic Managers mostly fill, can maintain consistency of intentions and morals and ensure that Efficient EM practices run well according to applicable principles or rules. The practice of Efficient EM is strengthened by the values of the Kalla Group, which were built to maintain the behavior of both agents and principals. In principle, economics is also an essential concern in the MaqashidAsy Syariah aspect to maintain quality and

quantity to ensure business problems. Aspects of such amount as determining prices are costs, production costs, labor costs, and other overheads. A market mechanism that gives birth to a fair or equal price. Attitudes took to earn profits that do not violate sharia. While the quality aspect must look at whether the object of goods is halal or non-halal, the legality of the transaction and the transaction mechanism depend on the release of the agent of a transaction from elements of fraud (gharar), manipulation (tadhlis), monopoly (ihtikar).

2. *Efficient EM Islamic Ethical Perspective and Profit Quality Masalah*

EM Kalla Group's Efficient Treatment

From the interview results, it can be concluded that Kalla Group's Efficient EM Practices have been carried out based on accounting policies made and applied in all Kalla Group's business units. All forms of procedure, selection of accounting methods of recognition, and measurement are based on an agreement with the owner. Efficient contracts become a priority to accommodate the company's interests in achieving the goal of increasing profits. The uniqueness of the Kalla Group is that some of the business units are filled by the owner to illustrate that the principal also indirectly acts as an agent. This practice can be interpreted as reducing asymmetric information between the agent and the principal. Kalla Group's Efficient EM practices serve as guidelines for implementation that are continuously evaluated to ensure company goals. The agent and principal agree to manage the company according to the target set so that there are no interests outside the company's interests. This agreement does not ignore the company's obligations to owners, employees, and corporate social responsibilities such as corporate social responsibility (CSR), and no less important is the company's zakat. Kalla Group remains consistent in terms of the company's internal and external objectives and maintains the ethics and business rules that apply to keep a going concern.

Implications of Islamic Ethics

The implications of Islamic ethics and professional ethics are significant as understanding and role models to behave in a good and moral manner. As exemplified by its founder, Kalla Group's business places great emphasis on healthy and rewarding business behavior. His example is bequeathing the company that has been developed and the behavior inherent in Islamic values and religion. The attitude of monotheism, honesty, and professionalism as a businessman is a significant capital in competing and developing his business. It can be concluded that the implications of Islamic ethics are powerful and embedded in the values carried out in the Kalla Group company to ensure the sustainability and blessings of the company's achievements. Therefore, Islam leaves no room for ambiguous interpretation, and individuals must adhere to the ethical system that Islam presents. It has been narrated in one of the Hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad, namely "An honest businessman will be among the prophets, the righteous and the martyrs on the Day of Resurrection." This hadith is an indication that a manager is encouraged in Islam to have good characteristics and behavior. The ethical principles of Islam that become exemplary for the rich are accountability, purity, truth, righteousness, caliphate, and forms of integrity. In addition, the principles of professional ethics derived from Islamic ethics are found in the form of professional behavior, encouragement of belief, professional competence, objectivity, legitimacy, and trust as a form of ethical principles applied within the business scope of the Kalla Group.

Efficient EM Islamic Ethical Perspective

Efficient EM Practices The Islamic Ethical Perspective in Kalla Group describes the application that is consistent and in line with efficiency. Accounting policies are set using Efficient EM by maximizing efficient contracts for company purposes. The agreement of agents and principals to use the idea of recognition and measurement is an essential concern in financial reporting. To maintain the consistency of the practice of Efficient EM, it is strongly influenced by the values that are implemented within the Kalla Group. Kalla's values that are in line with Islamic values can maintain the behavior and actions of each agent in acting and making business decisions. The values built by the Kalla Group provide another perspective to maintain Islamic ethical principles and professional, ethical principles in every agent/manager in the Kalla Group. Efficient EM The Islamic Ethical Perspective in Kalla Group was found to implement Islamic values and ethics to maintain the consistency of the efficient application of EM. EM efficiency maximizes the expected utility for each bonus plan contract, debt covenant, and political cost. This indicator is expected in the form of an efficient contract per the agreement of the agent and principal. The strength of Kalla Group's values with worship, customer appreciation, sooner the better, and being active together can be implied with the support and commitment from the manager. With the help of Islamic managers, Kalla Group can guarantee the behavior of fitrah, morals, niyyah, and ijihad to maintain Efficient EM practices by strengthening Islamic ethical perspectives following the values carried out within the Kalla Group.

Profit Quality Maslahah

From the interview results, it can be interpreted that the Kalla Group company is cautious in choosing the core business carried out in the company. This is reflected in its implementation. One example is the Kalla Group does not want to do hotel business as the message of the company's founder, Mr. Hadji Kalla. Furthermore, Kalla Group is also cautious in determining prices that can lead to market monopolies if not appropriately controlled. Also, in the business related to the construction of tenders, there should be no bribery to win the tender. This is based on the Islamic religion's values and teachings, which are very thick in the company's values. The quality of earnings in the Kalla Group is seen from the side of truth and honesty in bookkeeping and seen from the concept of sharia economics being fulfilled. Judging from the idea of quality fulfilling halal products, having a cooperation contract that meets the elements of the valid contract, and there is no element of fraudulent practice, likewise, with the concept of quantity in determining competitive and mutually beneficial prices.

The *maslahah* earnings quality construct model is found in the Efficient EM Kalla Group practice with an Islamic ethical perspective. It gives birth to the quality of *maslahah* earnings, which is formed in the quality of financial reporting and the concept of Islamic economics with quality and quantity indicators. When viewed from *MaqashidAsy Syariah*, the profit quantity factor within the scope of Kalla Group meets the requirements of good quality in terms of cost and price determination, market mechanism with fair and competitive prices, and market behavior that does not violate sharia as well as mutually beneficial business. Meanwhile, from the profit quality factor, if viewed from *MaqashidAsy Syariah*, it also meets the requirements for good quality in the type of business and products run by the Kalla Group. All classified as halal are also very concerned with the transaction contract model following the contract terms allowed in Islamic values and values. And also, the transaction mechanism does not contain elements or forms of fraud (*gharar*), manipulation (*tadhlis*), monopoly (*ihhtikar*), or exploiting the naivety of the customer.

The quality of earnings generated by Kalla Group is assessed starting from the business processes and efficient EM policies that affect the company's profit. The strength of values that are consistently implemented for all of Kalla's people can ensure that the behavior and form of the financial reporting process are following applicable regulations. The Islamic ethical perspective developed is the basis for implementing efficient EM following Islamic principles and values. The quality of earnings that is maintained is not only seen from a sound financial reporting process but also safeguards from sharia economic indicators.

In addition, the obligation of *zakat* becomes a vital priority to purify the profits generated. The business processes established in the quality system or *RumahKalla Management System (RKMS)* are internal control to achieve excellent business arrangements. Maintaining and maintaining values for every Kalla person can ensure the consistency of Kalla Group's business practices. EM efficient practices and business behavior both in terms of halal product quality and quantity aspects can maintain mutually beneficial prices. Various efforts that instill Islamic values and ethics in Kalla Group's business activities can guarantee to go concerned and to produce quality profits that are blessed and *maslahah*.

Conclusion

Based on the research results and discussion of the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn: EM practices at Kalla Group have implemented Efficient EM. This treatment is evidenced by several owners/principal statuses acting as agents, meaning that it can minimize asymmetric information. Both parties between the agent and the principal, agree to run an efficient contract form to maximize utility and company goals. Efficient EM ensures that the financial reporting process maintains the applicable principles and rules. (2) The practice of Efficient EM in the perspective of Islamic ethics in the Kalla Group Company can be described by the strength of the Kalla Group's corporate values. Values such as work of worship, customer appreciation, faster the better, active together, in line with Islamic values or ethics and professional ethics. The strength of these values is implemented on all Kalla people to maintain the moral behavior of each agent. Islamic ethical principles, corporate values, and behavior of Kalla Group managers as guidelines and foundations for maintaining the behavior of agents and principals in the implementation of Efficient EM. Kalla Group, which has implemented the Efficient EM policy, is still considered risky in the long term. These weaknesses require the construction of an Efficient EM application model. The construction model was developed by combining Islamic ethics and professional ethics as the basis for actualization for every manager or accountant in Kalla Group's business processes. Corporate Values that are in line with Islamic values and compliance with Islamic economic aspects can be a strong concept for constructing Kalla Group's Efficient EM model. (4) The practice of Efficient EM in the Kalla Group is developed from the perspective of Islamic ethics to keep the practices and behavior of agents and principals within the corporate values and Islamic values that have been built. The principles of Islamic ethics that are derived into professional ethics must be built and adhered to by agents and

principals. Islamic managers who maintain fitrah, morals, niyyah, and ijtihad can ensure agent behavior in each efficient contract to maximize the company's utility. Efficient EM practice by strengthening Islamic ethics can achieve the company's earnings quality goals. The quality of the company's earnings is maintained in the correct reporting process and defends the principles of sharia economics both in terms of quality and quantity and is obedient to the obligation of zakat to purify the quality of the company's earnings. For this reason, adherence to good care in the process of information and halal products can guarantee the quality of profits that are blessed and maslahah.

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